

In-vitro Antioxidant Activity of Siddha formulation *Panchathiktha Ghritham*

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Abstract

Background: The Siddha system of medicine employs unique combinations of herbs, minerals, and metals to promote health and longevity. *Panchathiktha Ghritham*, a traditional polyherbal formulation referenced in Siddha texts, has been ascribed various therapeutic properties. **Aim:** This study aimed to evaluate the in-vitro antioxidant potential of *Panchathiktha Ghritham*. **Materials and Methods:** The antioxidant activity of *Panchathiktha Ghritham* was assessed through four established methods: DPPH (2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) assay, Nitric Oxide radical scavenging assay, ABTS (2,2'-azino-bis-3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonic acid) assay, and Hydrogen Peroxide radical scavenging assay. Each assay measured the concentration-dependent inhibition produced by the formulation and compared it with standard antioxidant agents. **Results:** *Panchathiktha Ghritham* demonstrated a concentration-dependent increase in free radical scavenging activity in all assays conducted. While the formulation showed statistically significant antioxidant effects, the potency was lower compared to standard antioxidants such as ascorbic acid, gallic acid, and BHA. Nonetheless, the results suggest the presence of bioactive compounds with free radical neutralizing capacity, supporting its traditional use as an antioxidant supplement. **Conclusion:** The results support the antioxidant potential of *Panchathiktha Ghritham*, corroborating its traditional use for oxidative stress-related health benefits. Further in-vivo studies are warranted to confirm these findings.

Keywords: Siddha medicine, Panchathiktha Ghritham, antioxidant activity, DPPH assay, Psoriasis.

Introduction:

The Siddha system, an ancient traditional medical practice, often employs polyherbal and herbomineral formulations aiming to maintain health and combat diseases related to oxidative stress. Panchathiktha Ghritham, referenced extensively in Siddha literature, contains a combination of five bitter herbs in a ghee base and is widely prescribed for its rejuvenative and detoxifying properties. Oxidative stress, implicated in aging and chronic diseases, can be mitigated by antioxidants that neutralize free radicals. Most of the drugs in the *Panchathiktha Ghritham* possess the antioxidant, immunomodulator, anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties. It is effective in the treatment of *kalanjagapadai*.

It is currently hypothesized that many diseases are due to oxidative stress that results from an imbalance between the formation and detoxification of pro-oxidants. Oxidative stress is initiated by reactive oxygen species (ROS), which are produced as a by-product of electron transport in mitochondria. Prolonged oxidative stress can result in permanent damage to vital body organs, which may lead to chronic disorders such as heart diseases, diabetes, neurodegenerative diseases, cancer, and premature aging.

In recent years, there has been an increasing interest in finding natural antioxidants, which can protect the human body from free radicals and retard the progress of many chronic diseases. Natural antioxidants such as α -tocopherol and ascorbic acid are widely used because they are regarded as safer and causing fewer adverse reactions but their antioxidant activities are lower than the synthetic antioxidants such as butylated hydroxyanisole and butylated hydroxytoluene which have been restricted by legislative rules because they are suspected to have some toxic effects and as possible carcinogens. Therefore, there is a considerable interest in finding new and safe antioxidants from natural sources to replace these synthetic antioxidants.

Recently, traditional plants have received much attention as sources of biological active substances including antioxidants. Numerous studies have been carried out on some plants, vegetables and fruits because they are rich sources of antioxidants, such as vitamin A, vitamin C, Vitamin E,

carotenoids, polyphenolic compounds and flavonoids which prevent free radical damage, reducing risk of chronic diseases.

In Siddha system of medicine many herbs are used in antioxidant medicinal formulations which are called as Kaaya Kalpa medicines. These formulations have been used to treat the illness and help to regenerate the degenerative conditions and also help to prevent the aging. In this Panchathiktha Ghritham is one of the Siddha antioxidant medicines which is widely used in practice. Kayakarpam is one of the unique special therapeutic divisions in the Siddha system of medicine advocated especially for rejuvenation, decreasing morbidity and increasing the life span. “Kayam” which means body and “Karpam” which means ‘strong as stone’. Hence it means keeping the body as strong as stone. Kayakarpam provides both mental and physical wellness to the individual. Kayakalpa herbs are rich in natural sources of antioxidants and so it necessitates turning towards such medicines to meet this great threat. Balance between free radicals and antioxidants is essential for normal physiological function. Natural antioxidants are considered to be safe and bioactive. Antioxidants obtained from natural sources are the only alternative to synthetic antioxidants in counteracting the free radicals connected with disease. During recent years, many species of plants are used in the preparation of drugs and are consumed as food owing to their antioxidant activities. So, antioxidants with free radical scavenging properties of medicinal plants may have great relevance in the preventing diseases and in therapeutic properties.

Psoriasis is a chronic, immune-mediated skin disorder characterized by keratinocyte hyperproliferation, abnormal differentiation, and persistent inflammation. External triggers such as pollution, physical injury, and infections can damage keratinocytes, leading to the release of inflammatory mediators and alarmins, which act as danger signals and perpetuate inflammation. This sustained inflammatory response promotes excessive generation of reactive oxygen species, resulting in lipid peroxidation, cytokine release, and tissue injury, thereby creating a self-amplifying cycle^[2]. Impaired antioxidant defense mechanisms, including alterations in enzymes such as glutathione S-transferase, further disrupt redox balance and contribute to disease progression. Antioxidant therapies counteract these effects by neutralizing ROS, reducing oxidative damage, and interrupting the cycle of inflammation and tissue injury. They also restore redox homeostasis, improve keratinocyte function, and strengthen endogenous defense systems,

ultimately reducing inflammation, alleviating disease severity, and promoting skin barrier repair in psoriasis patients^[3].

Kayakarpam therapy, a unique Siddha division devoted to rejuvenation, reducing morbidity, and prolonging lifespan, exemplifies this emphasis on natural antioxidants. Formulations such as *Panchathiktha ghritham* are designed to neutralize free radicals, restore redox homeostasis, and support tissue repair, thereby addressing degenerative conditions and age-related decline. This approach is especially relevant for chronic inflammatory disorders like psoriasis, characterized by keratinocyte hyperproliferation, abnormal differentiation, and persistent inflammation, where ROS generation and impaired antioxidant defense perpetuate tissue injury. By supplying potent natural antioxidants, Siddha formulations interrupt this self-amplifying cycle, reduce oxidative damage and cytokine release, strengthen endogenous defense systems, and thereby alleviate disease severity, improve skin barrier function, and promote overall wellness.

Materials and methods:

The test drug *Panchathiktha Ghritham* has been purchased from GMP Certified Pharmacy, Chennai, Tamilnadu. It is a poly herbo mineral Siddha preparation prepared from twenty-eight ingredients.

Table 1: Ingredients of *Panchathiktha Ghritham*

Sl.No	Common Name	Botanical Name
1.	<i>Veppampattai</i>	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>
2.	<i>Seenthil kodi</i>	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>
3.	<i>Adathodai samoolam</i>	<i>Justicia adhatoda</i>
4.	<i>Peypudal</i>	<i>Trichosanthes cucumerina</i>
5.	<i>Kandankathiri</i>	<i>Solanum surattense</i>
6.	<i>Sittrarathai</i>	<i>Alpinia officinarum</i>
7.	<i>Vaividangam</i>	<i>Embelia ribes</i>
8.	<i>Devadaru</i>	<i>Cedrus deodara</i>

9.	<i>Yanaithippili</i>	<i>Scindapsus officinalis</i>
10.	<i>Chukku</i>	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>
11.	<i>Maramanjai</i>	<i>Coscinium fenestratum</i>
12.	<i>Athimathuram</i>	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>
13.	<i>Chevviyam</i>	<i>Piper longum</i>
14.	<i>Koshtan</i>	<i>Costus speciosus</i>
15.	<i>Milagu</i>	<i>Piper nigrum</i>
16.	<i>Vetpaalarisi</i>	<i>Wrightia tinctoria</i>
17.	<i>Ommam</i>	<i>Carum copticum</i>
18.	<i>Chithiramoola verpattai</i>	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>
19.	<i>Kadugurogani</i>	<i>Picrorrhiza kurroa</i>
20.	<i>Tamarai kizhangu</i>	<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i>
21.	<i>Manjitti</i>	<i>Rubia cordifolia</i>
22.	<i>Vasambu</i>	<i>Acorus calamus</i>
23.	<i>Modi</i>	<i>Piper longum</i>
24.	<i>Athividayam</i>	<i>Aconitum heterophyllum</i>
25.	<i>Sivathai ver</i>	<i>Operculina turpethum</i>
26.	<i>Kurosani omam</i>	<i>Hyoscyamus niger</i>
27.	<i>Kukki</i>	<i>Shorea robusta</i>
28.	<i>Evacharam</i>	<i>Potassium carbonate</i>

The in vitro antioxidant properties of *Panchathiktha Ghritham* were assessed through the free radical scavenging capability of the extracts, which was evaluated using the DPPH radical scavenging assay, the ABTS radical scavenging assay, Nitric Oxide Radical Scavenging Assay and Hydrogen Peroxide Radical Scavenging Assay

1.DPPH (2, 2-Diphenyl 1-2 picrylhydrazyl) Assay

The antioxidant activity of test drug sample PTG was determined using the 2,2-diphenyl 1-2 picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) free radical scavenging assay. Sample PTG at the concentration of 10 -100 µg/ml along with standard ascorbic acid were utilized for detection of DPPH scavenging assay. The final reaction mixture containing 1 ml of 0.3 mM DPPH methanol solution was added to 2.5 ml of sample solution of different concentrations and allowed to react at room temperature. Absorbance in the presence of test sample PTG at different concentrations of (10 µg, 20 µg, 40 µg, 60 µg, 80 µg and 100µg/ml) was noted after a 15 min incubation period at 37°C. Absorbance was read out at 517 nm using double-beam U.V Spectrophotometer by using methanol as blank.

$$\text{Radical scavenging (\%)} = \left[\frac{(A)_{\text{control}} - (A)_{\text{sample}}}{(A)_{\text{control}}} \right] \times 100.$$

The effective concentration of test sample PTG required to scavenge DPPH radical by 50% (IC₅₀ value) was obtained by linear regression analysis of dose-response curve plotting between %inhibition and concentrations^[4].

2.Nitric Oxide Radical Scavenging Assay

The concentrations of test sample PTG are made into serial dilution from 10–100 µg/mL and the standard gallic acid. Griess reagent was prepared by mixing equal amounts of 1% sulphanilamide in 2.5% phosphoric acid and 0.1% naphthylethylene diamine dihydrochloride in 2.5% phosphoric acid immediately before use. A volume of 0.5 mL of 10 mM sodium nitroprusside in phosphate buffered saline was mixed with 1 mL of the different concentrations of the test drug (10–100 µg/mL) and incubated at 25°C for 180 mins. The test drug PTG was mixed with an equal volume of freshly prepared Griess reagent. Control samples without the test drug but with an equal volume of buffer were prepared in a similar manner as was done for the test samples. The absorbance was measured at 546 nm using a Spectra Max Plus UV-Vis microplate reader (Molecular Devices, GA, USA). Gallic acid was used as the positive control. The percentage inhibition of the test drug PTG

and standard was calculated and recorded^[6]. The percentage nitrite radical scavenging activity of the test drug PTG and gallic acid were calculated using the following formula:

percentage nitrite radical scavenging activity:

$$\text{nitric oxide scavenged (\%)} = \frac{A_{\text{control}} - A_{\text{test}}}{A_{\text{control}}} \times 100,$$

where A_{control} = absorbance of control sample and A_{test} = absorbance in the presence of the samples extracts or standards.

3.ABTS Assay

This assay was carried out for the purpose of evaluating the anti-oxidant potential of test drug PTG against 2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonic acid) or ABTS radicals. The ABTS radical cation method was modified to evaluate the free radical-scavenging effect of one hundred pure chemical compounds. The ABTS reagent was prepared by mixing 5 mL of 7 mM ABTS with 88 μL of 140 mM potassium persulfate. The mixture was then kept in the dark at room temperature for 16 h to allow free radical generation and was then diluted with water (1 : 44, v/v). To determine the scavenging activity, 100 μL ABTS reagent was mixed with 100 μL of test sample at the concentration of 10-100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ in DD water and was incubated at room temperature for 6 min. After incubation, the absorbance was measured 734 nm. 100% methanol was used as a control. Gallic acid with same concentrations of test drug PTG was measured following the same procedures described above and were used as positive controls. The antioxidant activity of the test sample PTG was calculated using the following equation^[8].

The ABTS scavenging effect was measured using the following formula:

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Radical scavenging (\%)} \\ &= \left[\frac{(A)_{\text{control}} - (A)_{\text{sample}}}{(A)_{\text{control}}} \right] \times 100. \end{aligned}$$

4.Hydrogen Peroxide Radical Scavenging Assay

A hydrogen peroxide solution (2 mM) was prepared in a 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). Aliquots (0.1 mL) of the test sample PTG (different concentrations ranging from 10-100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$)

were transferred into the test tubes and their volumes were made up to 0.4 mL with 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). After adding 0.6 mL hydrogen peroxide solution, tubes were vortexed and the absorbance of the hydrogen peroxide at 230 nm was determined after 10 min, against a blank. BHA was used as the positive control. The percentage inhibition of the test drug PTG and The standard was calculated and recorded^[9]. The percentage radical scavenging activity of the test drug PTG and BHA were calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Radical scavenging (\%)} = \left[\frac{(A)_{\text{control}} - (A)_{\text{sample}}}{(A)_{\text{control}}} \right] \times 100$$

Results Analysis:

Percentage inhibition-

1. Percentage inhibition of test drug PTG on DPPH radical scavenging assay

Concentration (µg/ml)	% Inhibition of PTG	% Inhibition of Ascorbic Acid
10 µg/ml	15.39 ± 2.382	24.96 ± 2.969
20 µg/ml	26.37 ± 3.603	31.53 ± 0.9597
40 µg/ml	36.34 ± 2.709	52.47 ± 3.087
60 µg/ml	46.06 ± 3.621	64.6 ± 1.199
80 µg/ml	53.84 ± 1.933	76.01 ± 4.069
100 µg/ml	64.71 ± 4.737	90.57 ± 0.5341

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

IC₅₀ Values for DPPH radical scavenging Assay by PTG and standard

Test Drug / Standard	IC ₅₀ Value DPPH Assay ± SD (µg /ml)
PTG	70.43 ± 4.633
ASCORBIC ACID	42.43 ± 0.7923

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

2. Percentage inhibition of test drug PTG on Nitric Oxide radical scavenging assay

Concentration (µg/ml)	% Inhibition of PTG	% Inhibition of Gallic Acid
10 µg/ml	10.54 ± 3.323	30.32 ± 5.386
20 µg/ml	15.21 ± 2.1	44.2 ± 7.298
40 µg/ml	21.04 ± 1.835	56.48 ± 3.622
60 µg/ml	30.36 ± 4.62	62.25 ± 3.047
80 µg/ml	39.69 ± 1.202	86.01 ± 2.675
100 µg/ml	55.29 ± 5.62	96.27 ± 2.181

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

IC₅₀ Values for Nitric Oxide radical scavenging assay by PTG and standard.

Test Drug / Standard	IC ₅₀ Value NO Assay ± SD (µg /ml)
PTG	97.54 ± 9.462
GALLIC ACID	33.5 ± 6.576

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

3. Percentage inhibition of test drug PTG on ABTS radical scavenging assay

Concentration (µg/ml)	% Inhibition of PTG	% Inhibition of Gallic Acid
10 µg/ml	6.378 ± 6.744	31.44 ± 1.203
20 µg/ml	17.04 ± 10.08	54.23 ± 2.333
40 µg/ml	28.29 ± 9.477	62.93 ± 2.72
60 µg/ml	35.78 ± 11.41	79.12 ± 2.434
80 µg/ml	43.11 ± 10.43	86.78 ± 1.556
100 µg/ml	51.25 ± 13.39	96.96 ± 1.452

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

IC₅₀ Values for ABTS radical scavenging assay by PTG and standard.

Test Drug / Standard	IC₅₀ Value ABTS Assay ± SD (µg /ml)
PTG	97.68 ± 32.49
GALLIC ACID	23.71 ± 3.041

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

4. Percentage inhibition of test drug PTG on Hydrogen peroxide radical scavenging assay

Concentration (µg/ml)	% Inhibition of PTG	% Inhibition of BHA
10 µg/ml	5.289 ± 2.098	29.07 ± 4.996
20 µg/ml	10.22 ± 2.749	42.41 ± 7.407
40 µg/ml	17.73 ± 0.3613	54.63 ± 5.09
60 µg/ml	24.24 ± 2.53	60.15 ± 7.699
80 µg/ml	30.02 ± 1.17	74.3 ± 4.42
100 µg/ml	35.92 ± 2.383	88.2 ± 9.335

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

IC₅₀ Values for Hydrogen peroxide radical scavenging assay by PTG and standard.

Test Drug / Standard	IC ₅₀ Value Hydrogen peroxide radical scavenging Assay ± SD (µg/ml)
PTG	135.9 ± 10.97
BHA	38.35 ± 9.585

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

Observations:

1. DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay

The test drug PTG exhibited a concentration-dependent increase in DPPH radical scavenging activity. The percentage inhibition ranged from 15.39 ± 2.382% at 10 µg/ml to 64.71 ± 4.737% at 100 µg/ml. In comparison, the standard antioxidant Ascorbic Acid showed higher activity at all concentrations, reaching 90.57 ± 0.5341% at 100 µg/ml. The IC₅₀ value of PTG was 70.43 ± 4.633 µg/ml, while that of ascorbic acid was 42.43 ± 0.7923 µg/ml.

Inference: PTG possesses moderate DPPH radical scavenging activity, indicating its potential as a free radical neutralizer. However, its efficacy was lower than ascorbic acid, suggesting that PTG may be a supportive antioxidant rather than a primary one in DPPH-related oxidative stress models.

2. Nitric Oxide Radical Scavenging Assay

PTG showed increasing inhibition of nitric oxide radicals with rising concentrations, reaching a maximum of $55.29 \pm 5.62\%$ at $100 \mu\text{g/ml}$. The standard Gallic Acid demonstrated significantly higher activity, with $96.27 \pm 2.181\%$ inhibition at the same concentration. The IC_{50} value of PTG was $97.54 \pm 9.462 \mu\text{g/ml}$, compared to $33.5 \pm 6.576 \mu\text{g/ml}$ for gallic acid.

Inference: PTG exhibits mild nitric oxide radical scavenging potential, but is notably less potent than the standard. This suggests that while PTG may provide some anti-inflammatory and antioxidant benefits, its nitric oxide quenching capacity is limited.

3. ABTS Radical Scavenging Assay

The ABTS scavenging activity of PTG increased from $6.378 \pm 6.744\%$ at $10 \mu\text{g/ml}$ to $51.25 \pm 13.39\%$ at $100 \mu\text{g/ml}$. In contrast, Gallic Acid showed significantly greater inhibition at all concentrations, reaching $96.96 \pm 1.452\%$ at $100 \mu\text{g/ml}$. The IC_{50} value of PTG was $97.68 \pm 32.49 \mu\text{g/ml}$, whereas that of gallic acid was $23.71 \pm 3.041 \mu\text{g/ml}$.

Inference: PTG demonstrates low-to-moderate ABTS radical scavenging activity, with an IC_{50} value significantly higher than that of the standard. The results suggest that PTG contains antioxidant moieties capable of quenching ABTS radicals, but at higher doses.

4. Hydrogen Peroxide Radical Scavenging Assay

PTG showed a gradual increase in hydrogen peroxide scavenging from $5.289 \pm 2.098\%$ at $10 \mu\text{g/ml}$ to $35.92 \pm 2.383\%$ at $100 \mu\text{g/ml}$. The standard BHA exhibited stronger inhibition across the board, with $88.2 \pm 9.335\%$ at the highest dose. The IC_{50} value of PTG was $135.9 \pm 10.97 \mu\text{g/ml}$, while BHA's was $38.35 \pm 9.585 \mu\text{g/ml}$.

Inference: PTG exhibited the least antioxidant capacity in the hydrogen peroxide assay compared to the other models. The high IC_{50} indicates a weaker ability to neutralize hydrogen peroxide, a key reactive oxygen species, suggesting limited protective efficacy in peroxide-induced oxidative stress scenarios.

Discussion:

Antioxidant properties are of great significance in the management of free radical-induced disorders such as inflammatory diseases, dermatological conditions, cardiovascular complications, and even cancer. In the present study, Panchathiktha Ghritham (PTG), a classical poly-herbo-mineral Siddha formulation, demonstrated concentration-dependent antioxidant activity across various in-vitro assays. Among all models tested, PTG showed comparatively stronger scavenging activity in the DPPH assay, with an IC_{50} value of $70.43 \pm 4.633 \mu\text{g/ml}$, suggesting its ability to donate hydrogen atoms or electrons to neutralize free radicals. The DPPH assay, being a rapid and reliable method to evaluate antioxidant capacity, confirms the potential of PTG as a moderate free-radical scavenger.

PTG also exhibited mild nitric oxide radical scavenging activity (IC_{50} : $97.54 \pm 9.462 \mu\text{g/ml}$), which, though weaker than the standard, may contribute to attenuation of nitric oxide-mediated oxidative and inflammatory processes. This is particularly relevant in psoriasis, where nitric oxide overproduction plays a role in keratinocyte proliferation and inflammatory cascades. Similarly, the ABTS assay revealed low-to-moderate scavenging activity (IC_{50} : $97.68 \pm 32.49 \mu\text{g/ml}$), indicating that PTG possesses bioactive constituents capable of quenching cation radicals but requiring higher concentrations for significant effect. The weakest performance was observed in the hydrogen peroxide assay (IC_{50} : $135.9 \pm 10.97 \mu\text{g/ml}$), suggesting limited direct neutralization of H_2O_2 , a precursor of more reactive hydroxyl radicals.

The moderate antioxidant activity of PTG across different radical models suggests that it may not act as a primary antioxidant but rather as a supportive agent in oxidative stress-related pathologies. In the context of psoriasis, where oxidative stress, lipid peroxidation, and inflammatory mediators aggravate disease progression, the ability of PTG to moderately quench free radicals may help reduce oxidative burden and improve therapeutic outcomes. Moreover, the ghee-based formulation of PTG could enhance bioavailability of its lipophilic phytoconstituents, contributing to sustained antioxidant action in vivo.

Thus, the findings of this study substantiate the Siddha claim that Panchathiktha Ghritham has rejuvenative and disease-modifying properties. While its antioxidant potential is lower than standard references like ascorbic acid, gallic acid, or BHA, PTG may serve as a valuable adjunctive

therapy by alleviating oxidative stress, thereby supporting its clinical utility in managing chronic inflammatory skin diseases such as psoriasis.

Conclusion:

The study demonstrates that *Panchathiktha Ghritam (PTG)* possesses moderate antioxidant activity, with its strongest effect observed in the DPPH assay, followed by ABTS and nitric oxide scavenging, and minimal effect against hydrogen peroxide. Although PTG was less potent than standard antioxidants such as ascorbic acid, gallic acid, and BHA, its activity suggests that it may serve as a supportive antioxidant rather than a primary one.

Given the central role of oxidative stress in the pathogenesis of psoriasis and other chronic inflammatory conditions, the observed free radical scavenging properties of PTG support its traditional use in Siddha medicine. Its ghee-based formulation may enhance bioavailability of active constituents, providing additional therapeutic benefits. Further in-vivo and clinical studies are warranted to confirm its efficacy and explore its role as an adjunctive therapy in oxidative stress-mediated disorders.

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